
Building Character in Elementary School Students through Market Day Entrepreneur Activities on Perspective of Hasan Al-Banna's thought

Taufikin¹, Septiani Mutia², Miftahiyatun Nurul Hidayah³

¹State Islamic Institute (IAIN) Kudus, Indonesia

^{2,3}Islamic Studies, Postgraduate, State Islamic Institute (IAIN) Kudus, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The ongoing era of Society 5.0 in the world reminds educational institutions to prepare students from an early age, including the entrepreneurial spirit. Becoming an entrepreneur is impossible to do suddenly; there are several series for building an entrepreneurial spirit, including entrepreneurial education practices for elementary school students. Qualitatively descriptive, this research was conducted at the Islamic Elementary School (MI: Madrasah Ibtidaiyyah) Darul Ulum 02 Ngembalrejo Bae Kudus Indonesia, which aims to describe entrepreneurial activities in the form of market days in cultivating character. After the data is collected through interview, observation, and documentation techniques, analysis is carried out in the form of data reduction, presentation, and conclusion. The results of this study show that by practicing *Market Day*, students can position themselves as ideal traders by applying the principles of being traders who have honest and good character. As character education is the main view of Hasan Al Banna's educational thinking, the success of learning can be evaluated on aspects of honest character in its students.

KEYWORDS: Honest Character, Entrepreneur, Market Day, Islamic Elementary School

I. INTRODUCTION

The education problem has recently become an exciting study to discuss because students commit many deviations, and moral decline occurs in many of them. Education itself is an effort made by the nation to prepare the next generation for the sustainability of the community's life and a better State in the future (Mughtar & Syriac, 2019). Currently, the idea program that is the government's top priority is character education. Character education should bring students to cognitive value recognition and affective appreciation of values, which can bring them to real value experiences. For this reason, special attention needs to be paid to character education in each educational unit. Because regulations alone, without being realized by each educational unit, will not bring results. The right step is to apply subjects to students that contain character education so they can later bring character personalities.

Character development is an effort to realize the values in Pancasila, which is motivated by the reality of national problems such as shifts in ethical values in state social life, fading human awareness of cultural values, and so on (A. Ali et al., 2021). Contemporary dynamics carry the term education in an attempt to guide a generation that is in its infancy. Education refers more to the development of individual character maturation that prioritizes dynamic and practical aspects. In summary, it is a process of continuous self-development and formation (A, 2010). Character education includes the development of substances, processes, atmosphere, or environment that encourage a person to develop good habits in everyday life. Character education is not only related to right or wrong but also to instilling habits about good things in life so that students can have awareness, a high understanding, care, and commitment to putting virtue in everyday life (Zahri Aaron, 2015).

This moral setback needs to be faced with attention. The millennial era is a continued consequence of the third wave emphasizing globalization. Recorded in the history of curriculum in Indonesia, character education has been explicitly applied in every educational unit known as the education system that refers to ethics. This happened in the 1960s. Ethics education in all subjects reflects the priority of value education for each student (Zahri Aaron, 2015). The quality of education in Indonesia has recently experienced various obstacles, especially regarding the morale of students, due to problems in the education system itself. Among these problems are weaknesses in the education management sector, low quality of teaching resources, gaps in educational infrastructure, support from the government which is still minimal, the existence of thinking models that are still oriented in ancient times in society, and weak learning evaluation standards (Fitri, 2021).

The curriculum system of every change of educational material tends to change. In 2023, every education unit must be ready to implement an independent curriculum in its learning. The hope of implementing the independent curriculum is for the institution to produce knowledge with noble principles, civility, and noble morals to the ideals of the Indonesian nation (Muslimin, 2023). Character education can be applied through several things, such as habituation to start learning by praying, reading asma'ul husna,

Building Character in Elementary School Students through Market Day Entrepreneur Activities on Perspective of Hasan Al-Banna's thought

Muraja'ah, and the Qur'an together, and the habituation of dhuha prayers. In addition, character education can also be carried out with several practicum methods of existing learning themes, such as the Market Day Class. The market day class is a learning practice that introduces the world of entrepreneurs to students in the Independent Education Curriculum. This is contained in phase E. Character education through practice Market Day Class This is highly recommended because it can introduce various characters to students to create a strong foundation. Students who have a soul entrepreneur will grow into a strong, honest, and challenging spirit. Character education instilled in learners in practice entrepreneurs will determine the success and competitiveness of students in the future. Soul formation entrepreneurship is practiced in implementing Market Day to utilize energy and time to create an entrepreneurial learning atmosphere for students by reality.

Studies related to market day activities have been tested to build an entrepreneurial spirit (Dwinata et al., 2023; Concerned, 2016). Market day includes planning, production, buying and selling, and evaluation/reflection stages. The character desired by teachers towards students from the implementation of market day activities has shown habitually working together, thrifty, cooperation, responsibility, a sense of caring, confidence, hard work, openness, culture, tenacity, leadership, and sportsmanship, daring to take risks and have a future orientation (Aries, 2022; Asrofi & Mustikawati, 2020; Dwinata et al., 2023; Hasanah, 2019). Market day activities as a means of developing entrepreneurial skills (psychomotor) that contain cognitive processes (applying the concept of knowledge) as well as a form of affective emergence (character) (Lasmiatun et al., 2023; Sutarman & Nuriman, 2023; Wahyuni et al., 2022). The entrepreneurial spirit will be more attached if carried out early because it will equip them until adulthood.

Although many Market Day studies have been carried out before, studies related to Marketday combined with the thoughts of figures have never existed before, especially the thoughts of Education figure Hasan al-Bana. This difference then gave rise to the goal of cultivating character in elementary school students through the practice of entrepreneur market day perspective Hasan al-Bana. The results of this study will be a significant additional insight to strengthen education providers, especially elementary schools, and pay more attention to the importance of providing entrepreneurs from an early age to face competition in the present and future.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a case study conducted by researchers at Islamic Elementary School (MI) Darul Ulum 02 Ngembalrejo Bae Kudus, which has the full address of Ngembalrejo Village Jl. Kudus-Pati km 05 Bae District, Kudus Regency, where MI Darul Ulum 02 Bae Ngembalrejo Kudus is a private madrasah under the auspices of the Darul Ulum Kudus Islamic Education Institute Foundation. MI Darul Ulum 02 Ngembalrejo is a madrasah with an independent curriculum implementation program before the independent curriculum is established. This is evident in its learning system, which, in addition to offering superior programs, namely tahfidz, science, and ICT (digital), MI Darul Ulum 02 also has fifteen types of extracurriculars, both academic and non-academic extracurriculars which have so far been able to bridge students to be competent in all competitions both at the local and national levels. Uniquely, MI Darul Ulum 02 highly upholds the concept of "gusjigang" offered by Sunan Kudus. From here, the gusjigang culture is applied in the character recognition program by requiring market day practices for grade 2 students and work degrees at the end of the semester, which all students from grade one attend to grade six.

This research used descriptive qualitative research by placing case studies as the main design. The descriptive qualitative research method intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by the research subject holistically by describing in the form of words in a natural context by utilizing various natural methods (M. Djamal, 2015; Sugiyono, 2012). This research method aims to provide a detailed and accurate picture of the observed situation or event. In addition, this method also explores the context, meaning, and complexity of relationships between existing elements. The steps taken by researchers before being directly involved in observing the behavior of MI Darul Ulum 02 students during the Market Day activity and how the pre-process placed Market Day, Market Day, and after Market Day Done. In addition, other data obtained by the author through the interview process with the head of the madrasah, class teachers, and students who were directly involved in the implementation process of Market Day, as well as several journal articles and books that support the content of this study (Joseph, 2014). Researchers carry out data analysis through the stages of reduction, presentation, and conclusion to identify how characters appear in students during Market Day, which takes place by integrating the concept of character education from the perspective of Hasan Al-Bana. These findings strengthen previous research while adding alternative learning options, especially in cultivating character through entrepreneur market day activities.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hasan Al-Bana

Hasan al-Banna is one of the figures in the field of Islamic education. He contributed his thoughts on education to change educators' views regarding sound education systems and methods. Hasan al-Banna was born in 1906. He came from a religious and distinguished family. His father was named Sheikh Ahmad Abdurrahman al-Banna and was more famously called *as-Sa'ati* (Zaeny, 2011). The critical point of Hasan al-Banna's educational thinking is about character education in students. In his time, Hasal al-Banna designed practical worship education practiced by his congregation, personally and in the congregation. Among the programs initiated by Hasan al Banna is the discipline of mujahadah through the wirid al-Qur'an and wirid dhikr, which is mature in the hope

Building Character in Elementary School Students through Market Day Entrepreneur Activities on Perspective of Hasan Al-Banna's thought

that the feeling can always be with Allah (Umam, 2022). This is because the primary purpose of education is to form a human person who believes in God (Umam, 2022). The evaluation of education applied by Hasan al Banna is to cultivate an honest attitude of his students (Rahayu, 2019).

Entrepreneur

Entrepreneurship is the process of creating something different or unprecedented to increase the prosperity of individuals or groups. At the same time, entrepreneurs create something to benefit many people's lives. Entrepreneurs can be classified into four categories, namely, entrepreneurs in the fields of business, social, academic, and government (Radianto et al., 2018). The process of forming an entrepreneur itself arises from three things, namely, from birth, from the environment, and from practice. Birth means when a person is born into a family that has become an entrepreneur, he will most likely become an entrepreneur. An environment is a person who is not born into an entrepreneurial family. However, he lives and trains in an entrepreneurial environment, meaning he was not born but is in an entrepreneurial environment. However, he wants to learn and train to become an entrepreneur (Radianto et al., 2018).

Market Day

This word is composed of two words of English origin. Market day means market day. *Market day* is an activity by an educational institution as a form of sales and purchase training practices carried out by students where both have been determined. Implementing *Market Day* itself aims to teach people creativity, respect for time, how to solve problems to share with others, and how to make their own decisions. Moreover, *Market Day* is an entrepreneurial learning activity where students are taught how to market products to friends, teachers, or other parties (Hidayah & Ayuningtyas, 2022). The legal basis used in the implementation of the program *Market Day* is a National policy of National Character Building contained in the 2010 presidential regulation; this is associated with Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 1995 concerning the National Idea of Socializing and Cultivating Entrepreneurship, which mandates all levels of Indonesian society to develop entrepreneurship programs (Hidayah & Ayuningtyas, 2022).

Character Education, Entrepreneur, Market Day, Hasan Al-Bana

Character education is ethical education that involves aspects of knowledge, feelings, and actions. Based on the Law on the National Education System number 20/2003 article 1, paragraph 1, students must actively develop their potential. The development of students' potential is directed toward having spiritual strength, self-control, and personality to support provisions for students living in the community (A. et al., 2018). In the Indonesian extensive dictionary, character means character, psychological qualities, morals or ethics, and character (Great et al., t.t.). Education in the Big Dictionary Indonesian can be interpreted as changing the attitudes and behavior of a person or group of people to mature humans through training efforts. Character education is critical to be applied starting from the lowest educational unit because it is only possible for a person's character to appear in such a way with habituating character formation from childhood. Each individual has a different character. A person's character is formed from the family environment or community environment. Good character will display good behavior, and flawed character will produce lousy behavior. Individuals with good character can make decisions and are ready to take responsibility for every consequence of their decisions (Abdullah et al., 2019; Toharudin et al., 2019). In addition, individuals with good character will undoubtedly have a well-received contribution to society.

In the current era, character education is highly emphasized and must be realized. Many influencers have emerged who can bring their existence to the international arena. Education plays a role in creating the nation's next generation, who can develop students' potential by the times' demands. Hence, entrepreneurship education must be introduced to students as early as possible. Global industry competition every year has a reasonably high increase. The word entrepreneur comes from the French 'entre,' which means between, and 'prendre,' which means to take. This word describes people who dare to take risks and start something new. Then, the understanding of entrepreneurs expanded to include innovation (Wijatno, 2006).

Implementing Market Day was initiated as an introduction to the world of entrepreneurship students. MI Darul Ulum 02, as an educational institution ready to produce superior generations in all fields, always provides innovations for each of its programs, both superior and local content lessons. The development of the entrepreneur program at MI Darul Ulum 02 itself already exists in the development of canteens where the products sold are products made by MI Darul Ulum 02 education staff themselves but as an educational unit that is proficient in educational innovation, then followed by several aspects that must be implemented from the independent curriculum are entrepreneurs. MI Darul Ulum 02 chose to try to introduce the world of entrepreneurship to its students. As one of the efforts made to introduce the character of entrepreneurs, MI Darul Ulum 02 initiated implementing a market day class. Implementing the MI Darul Ulum 02 market day program has been ongoing for approximately two years. Market day is a mandatory activity for second-grade students of MI Darul Ulum 02, which is targeted at the practice of introducing currency (Indonesian lessons), addition and subtraction (mathematics lessons), selling adab (aqidah akhlak), terms of sale and purchase (fiqh), and training suitable communication methods between students who act as sellers and buyers. In addition, it also trains students mentally to dare to appear in front. Following up on the implementation of the market day, MI Darul Ulum 02 also carried out a work degree at the

Building Character in Elementary School Students through Market Day Entrepreneur Activities on Perspective of Hasan Al-Banna's thought

end of semester learning, which was attended by all students in grades 1 to 6. The concept of the work degree carried out by MI Darul Ulum 02 focuses on the initial phase of students, namely grade 1 to grade 3, filling in dance, drama, and poetry performances. Grades 4 to 6 held a work exhibition as an implementation of phase E, which contained entrepreneurship in the implementation program of the independent learning curriculum. The purpose of implementing this learning model is to arouse students' enthusiasm for learning because this kind of learning atmosphere stores elements of pleasure in students' hearts. A thing that can give a pleasant impression will undoubtedly be remembered for all time, and it may likely be thinking that must always be done until later.

The concept of learning that focuses on activities in the classroom seems monotonous and boring for students, so there is a need for new learning innovations for students, both forms of delivering material with concepts in Outing Class or others. Outing class itself does not always have to be done by going away from class; holding learning practices in front of the class can also be considered a form of learning Outing Class. In addition to fostering students' enthusiasm for learning, activities such as Outing Class are also intended to support students' skills beyond academic competence (Lasmiatun et al., 2023). The real target of market day implementation is one form of learning Outing Class. This is to develop students' courage in facing humans from outside. The market day, held in the middle of the semester, is intended to train students to dare to speak and offer their products in front of upper-level students, first-year students, teachers, and staff before they face a work degree at the end of the semester learning.

Each educational unit strives for the best things to equip students to compete in the global world later. In fact, in current conditions, to survive in the competition of life in the current era, humans need to have high creativity. Creativity usually arises from someone with an entrepreneurial spirit (Wahyuni et al., 2022). The child's mind and soul condition at this time is found in actual competence. The rapid development of technology and family conditions professionally valued enough to the upper middle degree makes students facilitate and depend everything on what they have.

Realization of program implementation Market Day Class in MI Darul Ulum 02 was initially only used as a solution to anticipate students snacking carelessly. Because there are many hawker sellers in front of schools that are impossible to prohibit from operating. Based on information conveyed by the Head of Madrasah MI Darul Ulum 02, "the children are very interested in snacks and toys. Because of the world, they go to get snacks and buy toys. As a second parent, it is also necessary to pay attention to children's health, both mental health, which must be separated from the culture of bullying and bullying, as well as physical health, which starts from paying attention to children's snacks every day because indeed if children are told to snack in the canteen which contains only ciki-ciki, it can be ascertained that a week and two weeks have begun to get bored.

In contrast, snacks such as grilled sausages, Pentol, cilung are more interesting" (Interview with Head of Madrasah Mi Darul Ulum 02, personal communication, November 22, 2023). With the implementation of a market day whose product content is homemade by each student, the condition of snacks is guaranteed to be healthy. In addition, implementing market day can attract the attention of students from other classes to participate in leaving snacks outside school. This can be proven when the market day opens; students' enthusiasm for outdoor snacks is much reduced. They are more interested in buying processed home snacks produced by each parent of the student concerned. Students sell food products, beverages, souvenirs, and accessories for their work sponsored by their parents. In addition, the second class homeroom teacher of MI Darul Ulum 02, who is indeed the target of implementing this program, also emphasized that "any activity takes the form of an outing class. It is very capable of attracting the attention of learners. Moreover, children do like to role-play. Learning and being able to recognize many characters will undoubtedly have an impact on the character of students, which leads to positive things.

We, as educators, always want to innovate forms of learning that have high appeal to students by orienting towards applying positive values. The matter of character education in MI Darul Ulum 02 itself has been carried out through compulsory habituation programs that are applied, such as in the morning before starting learning begins with reading prayers (learning prayers, asma'ul husna, and sholawat), muraja'ah memorizing juz 30, which is then continued with Dhuha prayers. However, this habituation is indeed oriented towards Islamic teachings based on the principle of worship. At the same time, we also want to apply the mu'amalah program to students to balance Between aqidah, worship, and muamalahnya so that the implementation of market day class is felt to be the right starting way." (Interview with Homeroom Class 2, personal communication, November 22, 2023). Following up on the content that must be met in the independent curriculum, there is a learning theme entrepreneur. The independent curriculum system emphasizes students' talents and interests by multiplying students' work or practicum. The market day has become the implementation of mathematics, PKN, Indonesian, cultural arts, and ethics (aqidah akhlak). In practice, the market day conducted by MI Darul Ulum 02 students is carried out through the following stages:

1. Preparation

At this stage, children prepare the products they will sell. Children produce home-cooked snacks assisted by their parents. They learn to recognize food ingredients and manufacturing procedures, and students are told the selling price. In addition to producing home-processed snacks, students produce various kinds of souvenirs such as bracelets, rings, necklaces made from beads, key chains, and other toys. Of course, each product has a different price. During active teaching and learning activities, students have focused on forms of learning that can produce products, especially in cultural arts lessons. This is obtained in the students' works exhibited on market day at the work degree event, which contained the results of carving crafts, weaving, and painting.

Building Character in Elementary School Students through Market Day Entrepreneur Activities on Perspective of Hasan Al-Banna's thought

2. Place setting (location)

At this stage, learners arrange a place they will use to sell. Usually, in the foyer of the madrasah, the location is comprehensive and strategic enough to be a place for buying and selling. Once the place is well organized, the children arrange their products on their respective tables, accompanied by a money box and the price tag of each product. The setting of this place is intended for the convenience of implementing market days, which take place during two different sessions to spend on products owned by students.

3. Implementation

The implementation of the market day is carried out at the first break hour. Here, the children who carry out the market day are already at the market day location and are ready to make buying and selling transactions. As with the reality conditions of buying and selling, there are bargaining prices and discounts written on each product with a discounted price. If many products are left, the remaining products will be exhibited again at the second break, which is at 11.35 WIB, so that the products brought by students can be sold out.

This series of implementation stages is the same as the description of the three entrepreneurial activities (Radianto et al., 2018), which is in the first stage or the lowest stage, the stage *to know* (knowledge). This stage of entrepreneurship provides definitions and knowledge about *entrepreneurs*. Second, carry out entrepreneurial activities. Moreover, the third is to deliver candidates *who are entrepreneurs* to be *entrepreneurs*.

Learning methods that can produce products are challenging to apply, especially in educational units at the elementary level. However, MI Darul Ulum 02 can provide learning methods that produce superior products even though it still needs the core label of MI Darul Ulum 02. A market day at the work degree event displayed the creativity of students who could be auctioned with prices starting at Rp. 50,000, such as cubit results from students' work in the form of vases from woven sticks, bags from leftover coffee wrappers, table decoration flowers from used plastic bottles, and even mask carvings that can be produced from the ring fingers of MI Darul Ulum 02 students. In addition, in their daily lives, many MI Darul Ulum 02 students have begun to channel their interest in the world of entrepreneurship; this can be proven by some students already known to have products that they market despite their status as resellers. An example is Bagas, a student from the sixth grade who receives orders for sholawat mafia banners; he once received orders of up to Rp. 400,000; then another student is Kanjeng, a sixth-grade student; he has a mobile legend top-up business which, per hero, he can market up to Rp. 150. 000; from the lower class, there is also Nadia, a third-grade student who sells traditional fans at a price of Rp. 3000; to his friends. This is undoubtedly good for their life provision because they have been able to innovate and want to be directly involved in entrepreneurship, which is still under the supervision of parents and teachers. Implementing market day can build honest character in students (Siska & Japar, 2020). This can be reflected in how children give change. Answering various questions related to their products, teachers at MI Darul Ulum 02 have realized a lot about the entrepreneurial potential of their students. They often transact buying and selling at school and tell the results of their respective businesses to the homeroom teacher. The principal of MI Darul Ulum 02 also salutes the students' entrepreneurial spirit. However, according to the age of the students, the principal only permits buying and selling transactions between students for a maximum of Rp. 20,000. About the narrative of students who own businesses, asked about their parents' permission said that before deciding to sell, they first asked permission from their parents. Because their age is sometimes still labile, it is feared that if anything happens, there will be adults who understand and can direct them. In addition, it is also intended that they are active with the results they get personally and then lazy to continue their education. All matters related to the process of child development, of course, parents and teachers are obliged to participate in it.

As one of the leading thinkers on education, Hasan al Banna offers the concept of character education by emphasizing honesty at the essential points of human self-formation. Likewise, MI Darul Ulum 02 has a vision of "the realization of madrasahs that excel in digital, science, tahfidz, talent, interest, and creative character, based on faith and piety ."As well as the mission of forming students who are proficient in the use of digital devices, forming the character of students who are creative in digital science, fostering the enthusiasm of students to excel in talents and interests, organizing intensive guidance for memorization of the tahfidzul Qur'an, motivating students to improve self-creativity, realizing the character of students to be competitive in every aspect, developing a National curriculum and a Religious education curriculum that Characterized by the values of Pancasila, applying religious moderation, orderly culture, discipline, courtesy in behaving towards others, improving teacher competence in learning innovation, organizing 21st-century learning and optimizing all *stakeholders* in the madrasah environment. The desire of both to realize an education that can bring students to noble character is a big goal. The implementation of market day class activities for students at MI Darul Ulum 02 is undoubtedly able to awaken the honest character of each student because the process of buying and selling, of course, teaches many things about honesty both from the time of producing goods, then at the time of implementation and the final result, namely the experience obtained by students after carrying out market day. This can be proven by the honesty of students who answer and carry out each *step-by-step* well. Hasan al-Banna puts the position of honesty to be number one that must be targeted in the implementation education program carried out from MI Darul Ulum 02, namely by implementing this market day

Building Character in Elementary School Students through Market Day Entrepreneur Activities on Perspective of Hasan Al-Banna's thought

program to practice the concept of muamalah in the philosophy of Sunan Kudus gusjigang to be able to mold the character of students as honest entrepreneurs.

Hasan al Banna often said that education is an effort from humans to change conditions for the better. He also said that education should be a pillar of revival because when Muslims are educated, they will understand their rights that must be received in full and learn how to obtain them. Hasan al-Banna said that the success of education could be achieved when there is the spiritual, intellectual, and physical maturity of the proponents of da'wah. From this, it is clear that the purpose of Hasan al-Banna's education is a manifestation of the ideal values formed in the desired human person, which influence and symptomatic in behavior, oriented to realize Islamic identity, namely forming the Muslim personality has the view that the essence of man does not lie in his physique, but lies in a clot of blood (heart) which when he is good then the whole will also be good. The heart is a part of man that can connect man with the secret of life, the secret of being, and connect between beings and the Khaliq. Therefore, Hasan al-Banna's education focuses on reviving the heart so it does not die and softening it so it is not hard. According to Hasan al-Banna, there are three solid educational foundations. The three basics are (Abu et al., 2015):

1. Complete faith
2. Tough love, unity of heart, and cohesiveness of conscience
3. Built to sacrifice to God with his soul and property

The three basic concepts of education formulated by Hasan al Banna are reflected in the vision and mission of MI Darul Ulum 02. The commitment of an educator in carrying out his duties is how he can provide teaching that can reach students competently so that what he teaches can be used for students' future success. When Hasan al Banna applies the principle of honesty to the final results or evaluation of education, MI Darul Ulum 02 emphasizes the principle of honesty at the point of character formation or habituation placed on each learning model, which here is emphasized in the market day program where indeed market day is considered the best innovation to be applied today.

Character education lies in more than just maximizing the development of abilities and human resources. However, it is also based on the strength of faith and the right intentions. Applying science without being based on a strong sense of brotherhood, attachment, and concern for others will only be a boomerang for the next life. The relationship between educators and students needs to be warm in learning systematics. Because this will influence students' interest in learning, there is an expression that when we love or like the teacher, the lessons in his life will be quickly received well because of the enthusiasm of students listening to what is conveyed by the teacher. For that, a teacher must be able to provide warmth for his students. This is shown by several learning innovation models that support character education applied in MI Darul Ulum 02, where teachers want to provide a pleasant learning atmosphere while paying attention to important points that must still be fulfilled in the curriculum.

The successful implementation of character education carried out by MI Darul Ulum 02 not only comes from programs considered excellent and appropriate programs but also from the consistency of educators who direct students to the best character. This can be combined with Hasan al Banna's thoughts about one thing that educators need to underline is that education must be held by people who have soul strength, strong determination, and strong spirit, have complete loyalty, are clean from weakness and far from hypocrisy, have a self-sacrificing nature, are not easily deceived by material things, and far from greedy. One example for an educator is to apply the relationship between educators and students in the form of sheets of personality competence where he can educate wholeheartedly and always pray for the success of his students

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Market day activities as a concrete form of entrepreneurial learning at MI Darul Ulum 02 Ngembalrejo Kudus have significantly resulted in growing character. Some phases of the learning theme in the independent curriculum are entrepreneurs. This phase is utilized by MI Darul Ulum 02 to provide an *outing class* learning model with direct and honest buying and selling practices between students and the entire school community. Market *day* learning provides fun memories for students so that they feel that with entrepreneurship, life will be more enjoyable because they can make money. In addition, students can also explore the characteristics of a good seller so that they can be applied in the future

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author entirely funded the completion of this research. Thank you to all those who have helped this research from start to finish, especially the school that has permitted to conduct research.

REFERENCES

- 1) A, D. K. (2010). Pendidikan Karakter Strategi Mendidik Anak di Zaman Global (2 ed.). Grasindo.
- 2) Abdullah, I., Hidayana, B., Setiadi, Kutaneegara, P. M., & Indiyanto, A. (2019). Beyond School Reach: Character Education in Three Schools in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 9(3), 145–159.

Building Character in Elementary School Students through Market Day Entrepreneur Activities on Perspective of Hasan Al-Banna's thought

<https://doi.org/10.2478/jesr-2019-0032>

- 3) Abu Muhammad Iqbal. (2015). *Pemikiran Pendidikan Islam*. Pustaka Pelajar.
- 4) Ali, A., Abdullah, A. Y., Hasanah, A., & Arifin, B. S. (2021). PENDIDIKAN AKHLAK DAN KARAKTER SEBAGAI LANDASAN TEORI PENDIDIKAN KARAKTER BANGSA INDONESIA. *HAWARI Jurnal Pendidikan Agama dan Keagamaan Islam*, 2(1), 38.
- 5) Ali, A. M. (2018). *Pendidikan Karakter Konsep Dan Implementasinya* (1 ed.). Kencana.
- 6) Aries, A. M. (2022). PENINGKATAN KARAKTER GOTONG ROYONG MELALUI MARKET DAY DI SEKOLAH DASAR. *Dewantara : Jurnal Pendidikan Sosial Humaniora*, 1(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.30640/dewantara.v1i4.388>
- 7) Asrofi, M., & Mustikawati, E. (2020). Menumbuhkan Literasi Keuangan Melalui Progam Market Day di SDIT Lukman AlHakim Internasional. *AN NUR: Jurnal Studi Islam*, 12(2), Article 2. <https://jurnalannur.ac.id/index.php/An-Nur/article/view/83>
- 8) Badawi. (2023). PEMBENTUKAN KARAKTER KEWIRUSAHAAN DENGAN KEGIATAN MARKET DAY DI SEKOLAH DASAR SOEKARNO HATTA. *Jurnal Elsa*, 21(1), 89.
- 9) Dwinata, A., Asmarani, R., Sarumaha, M. S., Hikmah, N., & Pratiwi, E. Y. R. (2023). Program Market Day Sebagai Sarana Pembinaan Karakter Kewirausahaan Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 7(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v7i4.6022>
- 10) Fitri, S. F. N. (2021). *Problematika Kualitas Pendidikan di Indonesia*. 5.
- 11) Hasanah, U. (2019). Upaya Menumbuhkan Jiwa Entrepreneurship melalui Kegiatan Market Day bagi Anak Usia Dini. *DEDIKASI: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 1(1), Article 1. <https://e-journal.metrouniv.ac.id/index.php/JPM/article/view/1599>
- 12) Hidayah, N., & Ayuningtyas, C. E. (2022). *Market Day Dan Karakter Kewirausahaan/Enterpreneurship* (1 ed.). K-Media.
- 13) *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia*. (t.t.). <https://kbbi.web.id/pendidikan>
- 14) Lasmiatun, K. M. T., Wijayanti, S. N., Afriani, Y., Riatmaja, D. S., Triansyah, F. A., & Gani, I. P. (2023). Membangun Jiwa Wirausaha Siswa Melalui Kegiatan Jual Beli (Analisis Kegiatan Market Day). *Journal on Education*, 6(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.31004/joe.v6i1.3748>
- 15) M. Djamal. (2015). *Paradigma Penelitian Kualitatif*. Pustaka Pelajar.
- 16) Muchtar, D., & Suryani, A. (2019). Pendidikan Karakter Menurut Kemendikbud. *Edumaspul: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 3(2), 50–57. <https://doi.org/10.33487/edumaspul.v3i2.142>
- 17) Muslimin, I. (2023). PENGEMBANGAN KURIKULUM PENDIDIKAN KARAKTER DI MADRASAH BERBASIS KURIKULUM MERDEKA. *Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam Darussalam*, 5(1), 108–130. <https://doi.org/10.30739/jmpid.v5i1.2093>
- 18) Prihatin, S., & Salwa. (2016). UPAYA MENGEMBANGKAN KARAKTER Jiwa KEWIRUSAHAAN PADA SISWA SEJAK DINI MELALUI PROGRAM MARKET DAY (KAJIAN PADA SDIT MUTIARA HATI MALANG). *Pancaran*, 5(3), 112.
- 19) Radianto, W. E., Efranata, T. C., & Santoso, E. B. (2018). *Generasi Enterpreneur: Anda Bisa Menjadi Enterpreneur* (1 ed.). CV. Andi Offset.
- 20) Rahayu, F. (2019). Substansi Evaluasi Pendidikan dalam Perspektif Pendidikan Islam. *Al-Ishlah : Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 17(2), 6.
- 21) Siska, Y., & Japar, Y. and M. (2020). Implementation of Character Education Values in Social Studies Learning of Elementary School. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(1), 1954–1967. <https://psychosocial.com/article/9680>
- 22) Sugiyono. (2012). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan RD*. Alfabeta.
- 23) Sutarman, A., & Nuriman, A. (2023). PENGARUH KEGIATAN MARKET DAY TERHADAP MINAT ENTREPRENEUR. *ADI Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 4(1), 7–12. <https://doi.org/10.34306/adimas.v4i1.1011>
- 24) Toharudin, M., Florentinus, T. S., Ekosiswoyo, R., & Sutarto, J. (2019). The Increase In Child-Friendly Learning Management Towards The Formation of Character Students in SD Inclusive. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1254(1), 012052. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1254/1/012052>
- 25) Umam, Dr. H. H. (2022). *Percikan Pemikiran Pendidikan Islam Dan Barat* (1 ed.). Harva Creative. https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Percikan_Pemikiran_Pendidikan_Islam_dan
- 26) Wahyuni, R. S., Juniarti, A., Hidayah, L. N., & Kawoco, N. S. (2022). Pengaruh Kegiatan Market Day Sejak Dini Terhadap Minat Entrepreneur di Sekolah Dasar Islam Terpadu Cendekia Taka. *JURNAL INOVASI PENGABDIAN MASYARAKAT*, 1(1), Article 1. <https://jurnal.fakultasekonomiunikaltar.ac.id/index.php/inkam/article/view/4>
- 27) Wawancara Dengan Kepala Madrasah Mi Darul Ulum 02. (2023, November 22). [Komunikasi pribadi].

Building Character in Elementary School Students through Market Day Entrepreneur Activities on Perspective of Hasan Al-Banna's thought

- 28) Wawancara dengan Wali Kelas 2. (2023, November 22). [Komunikasi pribadi].
- 29) Wijatno, S. (2006). Pengantar Enterpreneurship (1 ed.). Grasindo.
- 30) Yusuf, M. (2014). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan Gabungan (1 ed.). Kencana.
- 31) Zaeny, A. (2011). Hasan al-Banna Dan Strategi Perjuangannya. VI(2), 138.
- 32) Zahri Harun, C. (2015). MANAJEMEN PENDIDIKAN KARAKTER. Jurnal Pendidikan Karakter, 4(3).
<https://doi.org/10.21831/jpk.v0i3.2752>